

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 101004730

MILESTONE REPORT

Present and future AI accelerator applications

MILESTONE: MS18

Document identifier:	IFAST-MS18
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 24 (30 April 2023)
Report release date:	31/05/2023
Work package:	WP5: R&D Strategies
Lead beneficiary:	PSI
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

Based on presentations and discussions at two iFAST workshops, we review and classify present-day applications of artificial intelligence and machine learning in the field of particle accelerators, illustrating the various types of deployment and their demonstrated merits by way of example. Extrapolating ongoing trends and sketching possible future developments, we formulate a few open questions, and issue R&D recommendations. In particular, we suggest the construction of a testbed for self-controlling complex accelerators.

I.FAST Consortium, 2023

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004730. IFAST began in May 2021 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	A. Apollonio, R. Assmann, W. Blokland, E. Fol, G. Franchetti, R. Jacobsson, R. Ischebeck, V. Kain, V. Kubytskyi, A. Scheinker, T. Shea, V. Shiltsev, T. Torims, F. Zimmermann	CERN, DESY, ESS, FNAL, GSI, IJCLab, LANL, PSI, TU Riga, Reshape. systems	30/04/2023
Reviewed by	M. Vretenar [on behalf of Steering Committee]	CERN	31/05/2023
Approved by	Steering Committee		31/05/2023

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	MACHINE LEARNING CONCEPTS AND APPLICATIONS	4
2	ACCELERATOR OPERATION, COMMISSIONING, CONTROLS, AND BEAM PHYSICS	8
3	VIRTUAL DIAGNOSTICS	12
4	ANOMALY DETECTION.....	13
5	MACHINE LEARNING FOR ACCELERATOR DESIGN	14
6	THEORETICAL APPROACH TO MACHINE LEARNING.....	19
7	ML LIMITATIONS FOR COMPLEX SYSTEMS	20
8	CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND QUESTIONS	22
9	REFERENCES.....	23
10	ANNEX: GLOSSARY	25
11	ANNEX: PHOTOGRAPHS FROM BSW2022	25

Executive summary

This report summarizes presentations and discussions from two iFAST workshops, namely the Brainstorming and Strategy Workshop 2022 “BSW22” [1] and the iFAST Multidisciplinary Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Accelerators [2].

Artificial intelligence and machine learning (ML) are rapidly gaining importance in a large number of particle-accelerator domains, such as safe accelerator optimisation, automated beam operation, virtual diagnostics, fault and anomaly detection, accelerator design, and data analysis. The new tools may not only lead to better performance, but also lower the cost of future and existing machines and decrease energy consumption. Machine Learning already widely contributes to the exploitation of operating accelerator facilities. In this article, we illustrate dozens of successful developments at CERN, DESY, ESS, FNAL, LANL, ORNL, PSI, and SLAC, indicate directions for further developments, list open questions, and issue R&D recommendations. Amongst others, we advise that ML should become a standard topic in accelerator education. Further work is needed on time-varying systems. A question to explore is special applications for quantum computing in the field of accelerators. Most importantly, we should seek collaborations with ML experts from other sectors, and we recommend building a testbed for self-controlling complex accelerators.

1 Machine Learning Concepts and Applications

The general concept of machine learning (ML) and its relation to the two related domains Artificial Intelligence and Deep Learning are illustrated in Fig. 1, a few key ML concepts and definitions in Fig. 2, advantages and disadvantages of AI in Fig. 3.

Figure 1: Conceptual view of Machine Learning, embedded in the larger domain of Artificial Intelligence, and with Deep Learning as a sub-branch [3].

Figure 2: Relevant ML concepts and definitions.

Advantages

- Unique capabilities to find patterns in data
- Flexibility (from data exploration to predictions)
- Easy scaling with complexity
- Alternative viewpoint on known problems
- New developments and improvements can be consistently expected

Disadvantages

- Data quality is key
- Steep learning curve
- Model results are intransparent
- Resource intensive
- Adequate resources are necessary to follow the fast developments in this field

Figure 3: Advantages and disadvantages of AI [4].

Important ML features are 1) Automatic learning process; 2) Ability to process big data efficiently; 3) Ability to model complex non-linearities and identify trends/patterns; 4) Deep Learning (Neural Nets) allowing for a) better generalization than statistical methods; b) compensation for incomplete physics models; c) automatic extraction of relevant information [5].

Exploiting these features, several main pillars for applications of ML techniques to accelerators can be identified:

- (1) **Accelerator operation, commissioning, controls, and beam physics** – The main thrust of ML applications in this domain is the optimization and automation of operation. ML-based safe optimization of accelerator performance has been demonstrated at PSI for SwissFEL and HIPA; also, at ELETTRA similar techniques are applied (Fig. 4). Other concrete examples for this area, from FNAL, include linac RF optimization and longitudinal dynamics optimization, booster gradient magnet power supply control, “big data” booster control, orbit

alignment at PIP2IT using Bayesian optimization, FAST/IOTA RF gun stabilization and optimization, Main Injector (MI) loss minimization vs MI or Recycler Ring situation, stabilization of 8 GeV slow extraction from the Muon-Campus ring [6]; another intriguing example from the field of an accelerator is the ML classification of proposed experiments according to the ML-predicted difficulty of beam operation [7]. At the SNS, ML is used to reduce accelerator downtime by preventing accelerator failures and improving the target design. In addition, by offering sophisticated modelling techniques ML also enables researchers to deal effectively, and in new ways, with situations where only sparse data are available, such as laser-plasma acceleration [8]. At the SLAC LCLS, adaptive ML combining model-independent feedback and neural networks has been demonstrated for automatic control of the electron beam's 2D longitudinal phase space [9].

- (2) **Virtual diagnostics** – virtual diagnostics approaches enabled by ML effectively replaces invasive instruments such as spectrometers and screens, as well as fragile instruments, by a prediction based on non-perturbative measurements; it can be used furthermore for broken instruments (see also the next paragraph). Examples exist, e.g., from SING at PSI [3], and HiRES at LBL, and FACET at SLAC [10, 11]. Virtual diagnostics can speed up commissioning and save operational time by replacing time-expensive measurement techniques; as an example, see Ref. [12].
- (3) **Detection of faults or anomalies** – here, CERN is engaged with the detection of faulty beam position monitors via unsupervised learning, and the detection and diagnosis of lattice imperfections [12]; at DESY and TJNAF similar techniques are deployed for the superconducting RF systems [13]; at FNAL AI/ML is used for monitoring the NuMI target system, and for real-time quench detection [6]. Anomaly detection is also an important input for alarm systems (e.g., at ESS, Reshape, and CERN).
- (4) **Accelerator design** – machine learning can be used as a tool for simulation and prediction; this branch of ML application envisages the possibility of training neural networks on a sparse sample from high-fidelity simulations; the trained neural network can then provide quick, almost “immediate” results. Examples of ML-based accelerator designs are the optimization of the LCLS-II injector, the optimization of the dynamic aperture of SLS 2.0 [3], and the design of a muon collider's final cooling channel for transverse emittance reduction with the help of ML elements [14].
- (5) **Data analysis** – ML offers powerful methods for data analysis, as already hinted at in Fig. 2, with examples of regression, classification, and clustering; one example application might be the cleaning of beam diagnostics data; the ML-based data-analysis methods are applied not only to the field of accelerators, but in many areas of science including high energy physics. Data sharing can be based on advanced data storage formats such as the open-source Hierarchical Data Format version 5 (HDF5).

Figure 4: Statistical optimization of the electron beam trajectory at the FERMI@ELETTRA undulators; the average FEL energy was tripled in 8 minutes (8 iterations at 10 Hz) [3].

The key elements to be considered for applying machine learning are a) start with a narrow task, namely, e.g., the optimization of specific parameters rather than of the entire machine; b) the performance measure of the selected model, for instance, the beam size, pulse energy, etc.; c) usefulness of ML if or where no analytical solution is available, or for rapidly changing systems, especially when no direct measurements are possible. A key precondition to using ML methods is the identification of where ML can surpass traditional methods and how much effort is needed to implement a machine learning solution. Of course, it always needs to be assessed if the infrastructure for data acquisition available is appropriate and if there are sufficient resources to perform the ML training.

Data preparation is another key to the successful application of AI. It often is the most time and resource-consuming part, as illustrated in Fig. 5. Time averaging and other aggregation functions are among the tools, which can be used for the data preparation and reduction process.

Figure 5: The AI workflow [4]

2 Accelerator Operation, Commissioning, Controls, and Beam Physics

A major goal at CERN is the application of ML and Advanced Algorithms to speed up accelerator commissioning, speed up configuration switch times, and shorten turn-around time, by stabilizing the performance in the presence of certain parameter drifts through clever algorithms. ML is thought to complement classical models with “learned” models, in particular for (1) enhanced diagnostics, (2) automated processes, and (3) the push toward self-driving accelerators. Recent progress from Deepmind for a Tokamak control serves as an inspiration; the issues for the Tokamak involve time-varying, non-linear, multi-variate control problems. In parallel to similar efforts at DESY, CERN ML applications have already enabled speeding up the commissioning. Thanks to ML, almost 100 collimators in the LHC were correctly set up within 50 minutes – see Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Speeding up LHC collimator alignment with machine learning [15].

Another example of ML applications to accelerator operation is the alignment of the electro-static septum in the SPS, with 9 DOF addressed by the POWELL algorithm in 2018 and 2021 based on OpenAi Gym. ML allows building models from data via regression. An example is the modeling of the “Pole Face Windings” control at the PS. ML also allows for efficient use of beam time: ML guided the SPS scrubbing for LHC 25 ns beams. In addition, ML renders operations more efficient, e.g., by helping to interpret the LHC tune signal and providing a tune estimation algorithm on BBQ spectra that does not get fooled by 50 Hz noise. The ML with SimGan yields the most stable tune estimates from among a variety of methods. ML is also being investigated for deriving the LHC bunch-by-bunch parameters from AI tomography. Longitudinal beam parameters at injection will be obtained with ML, from a fit of longitudinal profiles and tomography. At present in the LHC this is available online only for a single bunch, and the actual procedure is too time-consuming. ML is also foreseen with variational auto-encoders for radiation hard Optical Fibre imaging, which may be used for next-generation beam profile monitors. The CERN ML development effort is directed towards

making numerical optimization “plug & play”, through offering a GUI, hiding the algorithm complexity, and separating optimization problem definition from the algorithm – see Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Making CERN numerical optimization “plug & play” [15].

Reinforcement Learning (RL) is a new concept in CERN ML applications. Numerical optimization requires exploration at every deployment. With RL, after training, the exploration phase is reduced to a minimum: one single iteration in the best possible case. This is achieved by the agent learning the underlying dynamics of the problem. The key is sample efficiency and continuous action. RL is expected to play a key role in RF manipulation in the PS and in the tune control in the LHC. In general, ML will be one of the paths to further increase the efficiency and flexibility of CERN’s accelerators. Already many successful implementations are available. ML offers a huge potential for high efficiency at low cost – i.e., ML solutions are very often inexpensive. Some challenges are still ahead (transfer learning, generalization → including more physics). The key to success is providing a framework and infrastructure: GeOFF, the Machine Learning Platform. The ML status at CERN is “work in progress”. The ML/operation team is trying to move from R&D to exploitation. Still missing at CERN is an overall AI vision for the accelerators.

An ML-based toolbox developed at CERN for optics control allows: (1) the detection of instrumentation faults, with no manual cleaning and repeated optics analysis; (2) the estimation of individual magnet errors, hence a better knowledge and control of individual optics errors (Fig. 8); (3) the de-noising of optics measurements, increasing the quality of the measurements (Fig. 9); (4) the possible reconstruction of optics observables.

Figure 8: Supervised-learning-based optics correction [14], providing an improved knowledge of quadrupole errors for both LHC beams, at every location of the ring.

Figure 9: Denoising of optics measurements using an “ANN” [14].

In addition to the already established results, new studies are currently ongoing in the following domains: a) optics corrections for High Luminosity – LHC upgrade, with particular focus on the local optics correction, and exploring the use of Reinforcement Learning for determining correctors settings; and b) exploration of more complex optics error sources such as various coupling optics errors and their correction.

At the ESS, an ML model for RF tuning of the DTL was developed. RF tuning aims at making the bunches arrive at a good time with respect to the varying RF field, and at keeping the bunches synchronized with the field while they are traveling within the cavity. This task is made challenging by the fact that the RF amplitude and phase experienced by the passing bunch do not exactly correspond to those indicated by the RF generator and controller (the RF modulator and the klystron and low-level RF system) due to losses in the waveguides and other construction-related limitations. A solution found at ESS is based on diagnostics which is sensitive to the time of flight of the bunches,

like the phase of signals of the Beam Position Monitors (BPMs). Model structure and hyperparameter values for the best model in the single- or triple-shot measurement scenarios are determined by an ANN as in Fig. 9.

The triple-shot measurement meets the tolerance requirements for phase and input energy, and nearly also the one for the RF amplitude. It offers better performance than single-shot and double-shot ones. The achievements for the best model are compared in Table 1 with the requirements. Targets for the RF phase and input energy are met, but those for the RF amplitude are narrowly missed. This is the model that is going to be deployed in the ESS control system and offers the possibility of far more rapid tuning than the traditional phase scans and signature matching technique [16, 17].

Table 1: Achieved and required prediction error for ANN-based RF tuning of the ESS DTL [17].

	Achieved	Required
RF phase	0.54 degree	1 degree
RF amplitude	1.32%	1%
Input energy	0.06%	0.1%

Four ML application cases from the SNS are illustrated in Fig. 10.

Figure 10: ML application cases for the SNS.

The following lessons were learned from applying ML to SNS accelerator operations: 1) continual learning and robust models are necessary to manage changes; 2) Success in the analysis might not be enough for operational gains – e.g. even a high accuracy might not be sufficient, in some cases, for a successful model deployment in practical operation; this suggests that as part of the standard ML workflow a target accuracy should be set as an explicit requirement before starting the studies (e.g. what is an acceptable accuracy in the prediction of a ‘bad pulse’ in a Linac?); 3) Modeling a system to generate data can take up most of the time, and 4) Retuning using ML resulted in permanent operational improvement. A machine learning framework was developed to follow the ML life cycle, illustrated in Fig. 11. This ML framework comprises version control, tracking of the model hyperparameters, updating the model per new data, routine tests to verify model validity, and improving the model with new features.

Figure 11: Machine learning life cycle [5]. The sequence of these steps also characterizes the ML application to future accelerators.

Contributing to accelerator controls, ML can also be used to forecast temperature evolution of, e.g., cooling water, oil..., and its impact on the machine, e.g., compensating for the detuning of an RF structure. Machine learning algorithms developed in other fields (such as natural language processing, robotics, image analysis, and trading...) are applicable to process controls and do not necessarily need to be newly developed for accelerator controls [16].

3 Virtual Diagnostics

A challenging and important question is how machine learning can deal with time-dependent effects. One approach is to develop adaptive ML-based controls and virtual diagnostics for complex phase space dynamics, such as in a Plasma Wakefield Acceleration. The starting point is the observation that adaptively tuned physics models are not fast enough to serve as real-time diagnostics. The theory of neural networks with nonlinear activation functions offers a possible solution. Several examples highlight the necessity of robust machine learning techniques for time-varying systems, i.e., for systems with distribution drifts. Adaptive machine learning (AML) can provide real-time diagnostics for such time-varying systems [18, 9, 10, 11]. AML has already been demonstrated for automatic longitudinal phase space control at the SLAC LCLS and the EU XFEL, and the HiRES Ultrafast Electron Diffraction at LBNL. The principal component analysis for electron-beam data is being carried out as part of the process. At the base of the AML method, the Encoder-decoder generative CNN for nonlinear data compression allows for low-dimensional latent space tuning. This method has been applied at FACET-II and HiRES for predicting the 2D projection of a beam 6D phase space [10, 11]. Predictions from an AML based on a convolutional neural network (CNN) can be compared with experimental beam profiles; see Fig. 12. An adaptive encoder-decoder 3D convolutional neural network was also already applied for coherent electron diffraction imaging for 3D shapes [19]. Work is also taking place on incorporating hard physics constraints in physics-constrained neural networks

to improve the robustness of ML predictions. For example, recently 3D Convolutional Neural Network PCNNs have been developed which are forced to respect Maxwell’s equations [20].

Figure 12: Predicting 2D projections of 6D phase space at FACET-II, comparing AML predictions and the measured “true” beam profiles [18, 9, 10].

4 Anomaly Detection

At FNAL, anomaly detection with continuous learning allowed the detection of 77% of anomalous events ahead of a magnet quench (Fig. 13).

Figure 13: Anomaly detection for magnet quench prediction at FNAL [6].

Another example of anomaly detection was reported from the ESS neutron-source rotating target wheel [16]. This ongoing thesis project will focus on developing software workflows for machine learning.

Anomaly detection often requires low-latency MLs. These can be used to detect “off normal” events via a trained “intelligent trigger” and then request readout via a timing system (Data-on-Demand extraction). Examples of ESS diagnostics systems to be read out on demand are Beam Loss Monitors, Beam Current Monitors, and Beam Position Monitors. ML-based machine protection inhibits further beam production when dangerous conditions are recognized/predicted – an extension of the “intelligent trigger” function [16]. SNS is working on detecting and preventing accelerator anomalies using the beam current monitor using models running on the FPGA for very low latency, a Random Forest model, or on a CPU, a Siamese twin model, as well as detecting High Voltage Convertor Modulator anomalies [5].

Examples of anomaly detection applications at CERN include the PS Booster alarm system [21] and the prediction of RF breakdown in CLIC high-gradient structures [22]. Latest developments in Large Language Models (LLMs) provide easy access to historical information and allow for faster fault diagnostics and problem resolution [4].

AI models often feel like “black boxes”, where for given (large) inputs a result/action is returned. Having control over the model decisions can be an essential ingredient for the successful application of AI models, especially in safety-critical applications. “Explainable AI” aims at “opening the black box” and providing insights into model decisions. Feature importance analysis comes “for free” when using decision trees-based algorithms for regression or classification tasks. SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) values assess the importance of each feature for model predictions [4, 22].

5 Machine Learning for Accelerator Design

Generic example applications of ML in the field of accelerators include magnet sorting for the optimization of DA, advanced magnet modeling based on the multipole errors measured for a subset of magnets, or even the design and optimization of a full accelerator optics ab initio.

One of the most challenging examples is the proposed future circular collider FCC-ee. For FCC-ee the use of ML is explored in the areas of dynamic aperture & momentum acceptance optimization using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). PSO is an evolutionary algorithm with both cognitive and “social” components, originally influenced by bird flocking behavior. PSO has been employed to improve the dynamic and momentum aperture of FCC with its high number of degrees of freedom; see Fig. 14.

Figure 14: FCC-ee dynamic aperture (left) and momentum aperture (right) for reference lattice (black) and optimized lattice (blue). The area of dynamic aperture is improved by 3.1% while the area of momentum aperture is increased by 18% - From T. Tydecks in the FCC-CDR, EPJ ST 228, 261-623 (2019) [23].

For FCC-ee, the number of degrees of freedom may be reduced by keeping a $-I$ transform between sextupole pairs, and additionally by maintaining the 2-periodicity (or, now, 4-periodicity) of the machine. Doing so, 294 degrees of freedom are left. This number is still out of range for brute force scanning; evolutionary algorithms like PSO are better suited to handle the optimization. The settings so obtained can be used to train an artificial neural network (NN) to predict the off-momentum dynamic aperture for different sextupole settings, as is shown in Fig. 15.

Figure 15: FCC-ee dynamic aperture predictions for different energy deviations from a trained NN model together with true values from particle tracking, for a test data set, which has been withheld from training - From T. Tydecks in the FCC-CDR, EPJ ST 228, 261-623 (2019) [23].

With such a model, the optimization process can be significantly accelerated since tracking can be avoided. The talk also highlighted the mesmerizing research line pursued by EPFL to “Develop an Expert System that emulates the decision-making ability of a human expert in optics design. Use the developed tools for the design of the FCC-ee.” (A person in the audience showed a visibly shocked reaction at the thought that this expert system would be used, as had been proposed, to replace the brain of Katsunobu Oide !!). Figure 16 illustrates this ongoing effort to develop and optimize the optics of a future circular using ML.

Figure 16: Schematic view of accelerator design optimization by ML, which may require a highly specialized approach – only simultaneous experts in ML and accelerators may be able to uncover the relevant features and train a deep neural network [7].

ML methods are also applied for optimizing the final ionization cooling stage for a future muon collider; see Fig. 17. Inverse ML models allow for a fast estimate of the design parameters,

Design of a muon cooling cell

- 25 parameters to optimize in each cell
- Expected to need ~15 cells

Figure 17: Muon cooling cell whose parameters are to be optimized [24].

Several approaches have been used for speeding up the simulations for the muon cooling cell, such as supervised ML (Fig. 18); the surrogate model and extremum seeking have been combined. The ML learning result was obtained from a supervised learning-based “Random Forest” model to predict cell design starting from required cooling performance. By contrast, a traditional approach would apply a few optimization steps, using e.g., a genetic algorithm. The table in Fig. 19 demonstrates that, in this example, the ML method clearly outperform the traditional optimization.

Figure 18: Using a trained ML surrogate model to optimize the ionization cooling channel for a future muon collider [24].

Cell	Beam parameters (end of the cell)				
	Emittance Tr. [mm]	Emittance Long. [mm]	Bunch length	Pz [MeV/c]	Pz spread
	300.0	1.5	50.0	135	3.5
1	295	1.7	79	125	3.6
2	283	2.2	61	118	4.6
3	270	2.3	128	105	2.4
4	255	4.8	210	95	4.1
	260	16.5	715	93	7.1

Figure 19: Results obtained by ML optimization (blue) versus traditional approach (red) [24].

Further potential applications of ML to the muon collider design include sample-efficient optimization, emittance computation for non-Gaussian beams, and creating an integrated model of the muon collider complex [24].

ML techniques can also be applied to detector design. A striking example is the optimization of the magnetic sweeper system used to suppress the flux of beam-induced muons at the proposed CERN beam dump facility (BDF) and its associated Search for Hidden Particles (SHiP) experiment. The physics case is based on 2×10^{20} protons on target and the dual detector system will search for: 1. Hidden Sector decays (“Hidden Sector detector”) and 2. Neutrino physics and search for Lightweight Dark Matter recoil signatures (“SND”). The primary challenge is background suppression, which requires the combined optimization of the muon shield and the detector geometry in terms of signal vs background – see Fig. 20. In order to maximize the signal acceptance the detector should be located as close as possible to the target.

Figure 20: Geometrical parameters sensitive to the ML-based signal-to-background optimization of the magnetic muon shield for the BDF/SHiP detector [25].

The optimization process includes 1. choice of a suitable working point for the detector with respect to the acceptable rate of muons; 2. iterative search for the optimal field map accounting for the full spectrum of muons expected from the dump, and the magnet engineering constraints. The beam-induced background flux is expected to be of the order of 10^{11} muons (>1 GeV/c) per spill of 4×10^{13} protons. In one technological option, the muon shield makes use of Grain-Oriented (GO) steel, sheets of 0.3-0.5 mm, for creating the proper shielding magnetic field. Optimization of field configuration is obtained by Machine Learning using a sample of muons simulated with PYTHIA/GEANT, tuned with spectrum measured with a prototype of the BDF target. In this option, assumptions are a 1.7 T average field in the core of six magnets of 5 m length and 10 cm space between magnetic regions. The whole setup is described by 56 parameters, and to reach an optimization a Bayesian procedure was employed. Although conceptually simple, the procedure of simulating the initial muon sample equivalent to 4×10^{13} protons requires 1 month of CPU with 1600 cores. The execution of the ML procedure illustrates that Bayesian optimization does not scale well for high-dimensional problems. In addition, the computing model imposes additional constraints such as making up to 100 guesses at once (with 16 nodes, parallelizing every function evaluation). The optimization was carried out using the scikit-optimize implementation of Bayesian optimization, which allows using Gaussian processes and random forests as surrogate models. The muon sample was reduced by a factor of ~ 40 , to 18 million beam-induced muons, speeding up the evaluation and evening out coverage of phase space, and using a separate sample for testing. Examples of simulated muon paths in the obtained shield configuration for different energy ranges are shown in Fig. 21.

Figure 21: Typical muon paths in the optimized BDF/SHIP shield, as simulated for different energy ranges [25].

6 Theoretical Approach to Machine Learning

An accelerator can be considered a “complex system”. For its data processing, one can distinguish between interpolation, fitting, and generalization. One major goal of ML techniques is generalization. The paradigm of “learning” is, at its very core, the minimization of a specific error function, through some method. The application of ML techniques requires a clear and well-established methodology. A linear model approach may use statistical techniques to execute the training. Nonlinear models can

be treated by logistic regression (sigmoid activation function) or through neural networks. The interesting territory to which the ML techniques may offer access is associated with “feature selection and information”. By implementing these two capabilities, the ML technique allows for reducing the number of input attributes: A smaller model size and better understandability plus faster training and running times result in greater generalization. This aspect also relates to the problematic issue of large dimensionality and the time dependence of a system. Although physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) are incredibly popular, they do not actually respect physics constraints. Recent efforts have been made on developing physics-constrained neural networks (PCNNs) to incorporate hard physics constraints into ML architectures, such as work on enforcing Maxwell’s equations in 3D convolutional neural network-based operators [20]. Such efforts, together with adaptive ML have the potential to greatly improve the use of ML for complex and time-varying systems.

7 ML Limitations for Complex Systems

Truly complex systems may impose limitations on the machine learning approach. The question “What is complexity?” was studied for accelerator in detail by V. Shiltsev. Complexity is something that we immediately recognize when we see it, but it is very hard to define quantitatively. S. Lloyd developed “Measures of Complexity: a non-exhaustive List” with 40 different definitions. Complexity can be roughly divided into two categories: computational/descriptive complexities, and effective/physical or structural complexities. Accelerator Complexity [26] can be defined by the following features: (1) Complexity to design (many dissimilar systems); (2) Complexity to build (# elements, # of systems, level of each system – “standard/off-shelf, special, unique”); (3) Complexity to reach energy = “make it work” (reliability); (4) Complexity to reach performance “luminosity” – These features are linked together by the CPT theorem. The CPT Theorem for Accelerators states that $C \times P = T$, with C: Complexity, P: Performance (log of luminosity), and T: Time to reach P. It is illustrated in Fig. 22.

Figure 22: Evolution of collider performance fitting accelerator CPT theorem [6].

Table 2: “Complexity” of selected colliding beam facilities [6].

	C , years	Interval
SLC e^+e^-	1.6 ± 0.1	1989–1997
Tevatron Run II $p-\bar{p}$	2.0 ± 0.2	2002–2007
RHIC $p-p$	2.2 ± 0.3	2000–2004
HERA $p-e$	2.8 ± 0.4	1992–2005
SppS $p-\bar{p}$	3.3 ± 0.2	1982–1990
LEP e^+e^-	3.3 ± 0.3	1989–1995
ISR $p-p$	3.7 ± 0.3	1972–1982
CERN e^+e^-	4.4 ± 0.4	1984–1997

The most complex collider to date in terms of the complexity of dissimilar systems was the Tevatron, especially when operated with the TeV electron lens for beam-beam compensation. The Sp̄S, LEP, ISR, and CERN colliders were most complex in terms of speed of reaching ultimate performance with a complexity figure of $C = 3-4$; see Table 2. The most complex future colliders to build include the highest-energy hadron collider, the muon collider, and colliders based on laser/plasma wakefield acceleration.

8 Conclusions, Recommendations and Questions

In recent years, the application of artificial intelligence and machine learning has emerged as a valuable tool in the field of particle accelerators, providing significant advancements in several key areas. These include the optimization of accelerator settings, enhancing performance and operation of the facilities, the development of virtual diagnostic techniques, the implementation of fault-tolerant designs by anomaly detection of the instruments, as well as improvements in data acquisition, storage, and analysis. By leveraging the power of machine learning algorithms, researchers have been able to achieve higher levels of efficiency in the treatment of complex systems, ultimately contributing to a better understanding of the fundamentals. This interdisciplinary approach has not only accelerated scientific discoveries in the field of accelerator physics, but it is expected to usher in novel approaches in the design and implementation of instrumentation.

In a final discussion at the brainstorming & strategy workshop BWS2022, all workshop participants unanimously agreed on the following conclusions.

- Machine Learning already widely contributes to the exploitation of operating accelerator facilities – dozens of successful developments at CERN, DESY, FNAL, LANL, PSI, and SLAC.
- We expect that ML will become a community standard for the analysis of non-linear dependencies and an everyday synergetic tool for all accelerator physics investigations applied to realistic accelerators.
- ML should be used for the design optimization of future machines. ML will be instrumental in achieving the highest beam performance, as exemplified by accelerators for dark sector research.
- Further work is needed on adaptive ML for time-varying systems.
- A question to explore: is there an additional benefit or are there special applications for quantum computing in the field of accelerators?
- We should seek collaborations with ML experts from other sectors.
- We recommend building a testbed for self-controlling complex accelerators.
- ML should be a regular topic in accelerator education.

While artificial intelligence and machine learning have made remarkable progress in various domains, including particle accelerators, it is unlikely that AI will completely replace accelerator experts in the foreseeable future. Human expertise and experience remain invaluable in areas such as problem-solving, creative thinking, interpreting complex data, and, particularly, adapting to unforeseen situations.

AI and ML can undoubtedly assist accelerator experts and operators by automating routine tasks, and by supporting the analysis of data. They can perform a high volume of automated analysis, pointing the experts to insights that may not be easily discernible in large data sets. The collaboration between AI and human experts is expected to be the most effective approach, as it combines the strength of both entities, paving the way to significant breakthroughs and innovations in particle accelerators.

9 References

- [1] [ARIES WP6 APEC & iFAST WP5.2 PAF joint Brainstorming & Strategy Workshop \(BSW22\)](#), Valencia, 30 March – 1 April 2022.
- [2] iFAST [Multidisciplinary Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Accelerators](#), as part of the 2nd Annual iFAST Meeting, Trieste, 20 April 2023.
- [3] R. Ischebeck, “Machine Learning Landscape”, iFAST BSW2022; <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1133593>
- [4] A. Apollonio, “ML-driven optimization of operation and maintenance of future accelerators,” iFAST Multidisciplinary Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Accelerators, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1204855/sessions/475411/#20230420>
- [5] W. Blokland, “ML/AI projects at Oak Ridge,” iFAST Multidisciplinary Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Accelerators, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1204855/sessions/475411/#20230420>; W. Blokland et al., “Uncertainty aware anomaly detection to predict errant beam pulses in the Oak Ridge Spallation Neutron Source accelerator,” [Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 25, 122802](#) (2022).
- [6] V. Shiltsev, “Machine learning /AI for accelerators at Fermilab and surroundings?”, iFAST BSW2022; <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1133593>
- [7] G. Franchetti, “Machine Learning Challenges”, iFAST BSW2022; <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1133593>
- [8] A. Döpp et al., “Data-driven Science and Machine Learning Methods in Laser-Plasma Physics,” [arXiv 2212.00026](#) (2022)
- [9] A. Scheinker et al., “Demonstration of Model-Independent Control of the Longitudinal Phase Space of Electron Beams in the Linac-Coherent Light Source with Femtosecond Resolution,” [Phys. Rev. Lett. 121, 044801](#) (2018)
- [10] A. Scheinker, “Adaptive machine learning for time-varying systems: low dimensional latent space tuning,” [JINST 16 P10008](#) (2021)
- [11] A. Scheinker, et al. "Adaptive autoencoder latent space tuning for more robust machine learning beyond the training set for six-dimensional phase space diagnostics of a time-varying ultrafast electron-diffraction compact accelerator." *Physical Review E* 107.4 (2023): 045302. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.107.045302>
- [12] E. Fol et al., “Experimental Demonstration of Machine Learning Application in LHC Optics Commissioning”, JACoW IPAC 2022 (2022) 359-362
- [13] C. Tennant et al., “Superconducting radio-frequency cavity fault classification using machine learning at Jefferson Laboratory,” [Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 23, 114601](#) (2020)

- [14] E. Fol, “Machine learning applications at the LHC and for future colliders (including muons)”, iFAST BSW2022; <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1133593>
- [15] V. Kain, “Overview of Machine Learning Prospects for the CERN accelerator complex”, iFAST BSW2022; <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1133593>
- [16] T. Shea, “Overview of AI Activities for the ESS Accelerator,” iFAST Multidisciplinary Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Accelerators, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1204855/sessions/475411/#20230420>
- [17] A. H. Nejad. “Developing an ML-based model for RF tuning of the DTL machine at ESS.” Master thesis, Lund University, 2023. To be published.
- [18] A. Scheinker, “Adaptive Machine Learning for Time Dependent Effects in Accelerators”, iFAST BSW2022; <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1133593>
- [19] A. Scheinker and R. Pokharel. "Adaptive 3D convolutional neural network-based reconstruction method for 3D coherent diffraction imaging." *Journal of Applied Physics* 128.18 (2020): 184901. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0014725>
- [20] A. Scheinker and R. Pokharel. "Physics-constrained 3D convolutional neural networks for electrodynamics." *APL Machine Learning* 1.2 (2023): 026109. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0132433>
- [21] L. Felsberger et al., “[Explainable Deep Learning for Fault Prognostics in Complex Systems: A Particle Accelerator Use-Case](#),” 4th International Cross-Domain Conference for Machine Learning and Knowledge Extraction (CD-MAKE), Aug 2020, Dublin, Ireland. pp.139-158, ff10.1007/978-3-030-57321-8_8ff. fihal-03414728
- [22] C. Obermair et al., “Explainable machine learning for breakdown prediction in high gradient rf cavities,” [Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams](#) **25**, 104601 (2022)
- [23] F. Zimmermann, “Possible ML applications for the FCC,” iFAST BSW2022; <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1133593>
- [24] E. Fol, “Machine Learning application in accelerators operation and design,” iFAST Multidisciplinary Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Accelerators, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1204855/sessions/475411/#20230420>
- [25] R. Jacobsson, “Dark Sector landscape and future search strategies,” iFAST BSW2022; <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1133593>
- [26] O. Rey Orozco et al., Availability allocation to particle accelerators subsystems by complexity criteria, 9th International Particle Accelerator Conference IPAC2018, WEPAF075 , Vancouver, BC, Canada

10 Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AML	Adaptative Machine Learning
DA	Dynamic Aperture
ML	Machine Learning
NN	Neural Network
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization

11 Annex: Photographs from BSW2022

Figures 17 presents three snapshots from the iFAST BSW22 workshop.

Fig. 17: Three photographs from ML dinner discussions at BSW22 in Valencia.